

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF BLENDED LEARNING AND TRADITIONAL TEACHING ON SENIOR SECONDARY STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

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Abstract:

Blended learning is an innovative instructional approach that integrates traditional face-to-face classroom teaching with online or digital learning components. It has increasingly gained attention among educators due to its potential to enhance teaching and learning processes. By combining the strengths of conventional instruction and technology-based learning, blended learning promotes greater student engagement, supports individualized learning experiences, and improves accessibility to educational resources. According to Garrison and Kanuka (2004), this approach creates a more flexible and interactive learning environment that fosters deeper understanding and learner autonomy. The integration of classroom-based instruction with digital platforms enables students to learn at their own pace while still benefiting from direct teacher guidance. As educational systems continue to evolve with technological advancement, blended learning is becoming a key strategy for improving instructional delivery and academic experiences. This study explores the conceptual foundation of blended learning and its relevance in modern education systems, particularly in enhancing student-centered learning environments.

Keywords: *Blended learning; Traditional teaching; Digital learning; Student engagement; Educational technology*

INTRODUCTION

Blended learning is an innovative learning approach which combines traditional or conventional face-to-face instruction with online or digital learning elements and has gained increasing attention among educators. This approach has the potential to leverage the strengths of both traditional and technology-enabled learning, leading to enhanced student engagement, personalized instruction, and improved academic outcomes (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004). Blended learning integrates the best aspects of classroom instruction and online learning, providing students with a more flexible and personalized learning experience. This method involves the use of digital tools and resources, such as Learning Management Systems (LMS), video lectures, online quizzes, and discussion forums, alongside conventional classroom teaching. The goal is to create a more interactive and engaging learning environment that

can cater for the diverse needs of students (Graham, 2006). It should be accepted that today's generation is familiar with technology; hence they prefer to access their phone or laptop than to save

piles on papers containing information they are looking for, hence, students can find out the files they have and read e-books. Conventional classroom teaching methods such as lecture-based instruction and textbook-centered learning, have often been criticized for their limited ability to engage students and promote deeper understanding of the subject matter (Kaciuba, 2014). The integration of blended learning approaches in teaching and learning process could potentially address these limitations by providing a more diverse and interactive learning experience (Waweru & Omwenga, 2015) In a conventional face-to-face classroom approach, the teacher physically stands before the students and gives out the learning materials, using a variety of teaching methods, and assesses the students through home works and class activities and assignments and class activities are given by the teacher to evaluate students comprehension of what is taught. According to Cooper (2018), the conventional classroom approach supports socialization among learners and enhances motivation through the learning process. It encourages in-person instruction where the teacher takes the center stage. However, this approach may not consider students individual learning style, and also may not be flexible enough for self-paced learning. As a result, the conventional classroom approach may not be student-centered as students' participation may be restricted to only what the teacher permits in class. Integrating technology into the teaching and learning process has helped to close the gap created by conventional classroom approach. Academic achievement is a multifaceted construct that comprises different domains of learning and covers a broad variety of educational outcomes. Academic achievement according to Adeyemi (2008) is the scholastic standing of a student at a given moment. It has to do with the successful accomplishment of goal(s). The purpose of testing an achievement is to help the teacher and the students evaluate and estimate the degree of success attained in learning a given concept. Adeyemi stressed further that it is as useful in testing the retention of information and skill and determining the efficiency of instruction. One of the issues at stake in education today is students' achievement measure in relation to teaching and the overall success of learning outcome. Academic achievement represents performance outcomes of the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals. Academic achievement is commonly measured by examination or continuous assessment, but there is no general agreement on how it is best ascertained.

Lagos state has six educational districts comprising 672 secondary schools (Lagos State Ministry of Education, 2019). However, the problem of poor academic performance of students especially at the senior secondary school level in Nigeria has been a source of concern for educators and policymakers. Traditional teaching methods which often rely heavily on lecture-based instruction and rote learning, have been criticized for failing to engage students and promote deeper understanding of concepts (Adekunle & Awolere, 2019; Onyesom & Ashibogwu, 2013). The problem of students' poor performance may be as a result of teaching approach and learning environment, among other factors, and its ripple effect on society calls for the need to try new approaches. The traditional mode of lesson delivery, according to Redmond (2011), is still dominant in most schools in the country, despite its limitations which include inadequate one to one teacher-student interactions, delayed feedback, and limitations in visual aids and materials that the instructor can use in a class session which affects learners' performance (Nuruzzaman, 2016). Lin, Tseng and Chiang (2017) argue that using the conventional classroom mode of instruction move all students through the curriculum at the same pace, regardless of mastery since the instructor has little time to assist individual student, and at home students have no one to turn to for assistance thus some learners end up not performing well. As a result of these

drawbacks and the increasing prevalence of information and communication technology and the internet, online learning has emerged (Viz & Kaur, 2017). In recent years, the concept of blended learning has gained traction as a potential solution to improve student engagement and learning outcomes in various subject areas. Blended learning as an emerging concept has been extensively researched by scholars in examining its effect on students' academic achievement, little has been published on its nexus with academic achievement locally when compared with developed countries in which the use of technology has advanced more robust learning system in the area of social learning, mobile learning, interactive and collaborative learning, cloud computing etc., all geared toward enhancing creative learning. Therefore, if e-learning is applied in its blended form to the teaching and learning process, what would be its effect on students' academic achievement and retention? This is the problem this study sought to address. The specific objectives are to find out if blended learning approach is used in senior secondary schools in Nigeria; and to determine the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught using blended learning and those taught using conventional classroom approach in private and public secondary schools. This study is significant to provide the basis for policy development and resource allocation and to enhance the quality of education. By exploring the impact of blended learning on students' engagement and motivation, the study can provide insights into how digital tools and online resources can make learning activities more interactive and appealing to students leading to better retention of knowledge and improved academic performance. It will guide investments in technology infrastructure, ensuring that schools are well-equipped to support blended learning and that students have equitable access to digital resources.

Teachers, Conventional Classroom Approach and Academic Achievement in Schools

Izuagba (2018) described teaching as the interaction between the teacher and the learner, or the learner and other learners under the guidance of the teacher from which learning ensues. In other words, teaching refers to series of interrelated activities designed by the teacher using materials/resources drawn from the learners' experiential background in order to enable the learner to concretize knowledge. Teaching is thus, an input with output in mind. That output or expected outcome is learning. Teaching and learning are opposite sides of the same coin. It is not possible to talk of teaching if the rationale behind it is not to bring about learning. Also, Anusiem (2009) defined learning as "any enduring change in behaviour that is as a result of experience which cause people to face later life situation differently". Both teaching and learning have been constrained by many factors which include wrong instructional methodology and evaluation method and inadequate interest on the part of the students (Yusuf and Ehiamentolor, 2006). Teachers remain the significant factor in the quality and standard of education at all levels, this implies that quality and mental health of teachers can affect the teaching and learning process (Fullan & Stiegelbauer, 2009). This validates the truism that the quality of our schools cannot be better than the quality of the teachers we have. Efiog (2005) stated that another problem inhibiting the traditional teaching in Nigeria is inadequate textbooks, workbooks and other teaching aids. Imogen (2018) also posited that the conventional classroom approach encourages physical collaboration which is needed for constructive development of learners. Some of the challenges prevalent in the face-to-face approach is that learning can be stifled as only dominant personalities in the class may take the bulk of discussions (Danbury, 2018). Students who are introverted may be sidelined as they may not want to struggle with the extroverted students. Another challenge, according to Doskocil, (2016) is that students have different learning speed, comprehension and assimilation levels. The face-to-face approach may

not give room for the teacher to put students' individual difference into consideration, and sometimes the teacher is driven to finish the delivery of learning content within the stipulated time which may hinder the teacher from focusing on the learning needs of the students. On poor performance of student, Ogunu (2000) noted that poor academic performance is a problem in Nigerian secondary schools public examinations. The poor performance of students was 42.20%, 41.98%, and 48.90 in 2004, 2005 and 2006 respectively (WAEC, 2006). Several authors have identified the factors causing this problem to include lack of adequate instructional materials and/or ineffective teaching method. Uwameiye and Ogunbameru (2005) blamed this on expository approach used in our schools in which the teacher stands most of the time giving verbal explanations in the form of talk-and-chalk while the students listen and write notes from the chalk-board. The authors further stated that such inadequate and limited teaching method tends to negatively affect the learner's views of practical concepts and associated methods. There are other teaching methods which the teachers have been using to deliver their subjects. Using the right method involves taking into consideration the topic to be taught, time available, resources available, class size, type of learners to be taught, etc.

Concept of Blended Learning Approach

In as much as the use of blended learning might date back to before the advent of technology (Bryan & Volchenkova, 2016), scholars started documenting blended learning in 2006. Today a number of books and articles on blended learning have been published. Scholars have defined blended learning as a mix of the best features of the traditional face-to-face and the on-line learning so that instruction occurs both in the classroom and online (through technology) where the online component becomes a natural extension of traditional classroom learning so as to deliver valuable educational experience to students (Nuruzzaman, 2016). Blended learning is that approach that brings together different learning models to create a learning environment most suitable for the students. According to Kiviniemi (2014) blended learning approach should not be viewed as a strange mix of the two approaches (online and traditional approach) but a synchronized approach that is now seen as working together. According to Lalima and Dangwal (2017), blended learning is an innovative approach that encourages the synchronization of the advantages of both traditional teaching in classroom and ICT-supported learning modules (offline or online). The definition of blended learning as the combination of online learning approach and face-to-face approach has been contested as reported by Benson, Anderson, and Ooms (2011). The contest was as a result of the argument that such definition ignores the need for course design and re-engineering of the pedagogical process (Vaughan cited in Benson, Anderson & Ooms, 2011). That is, blended learning goes beyond introducing technology to the traditional classroom teaching; it exceeds putting some educational content online for easy access by the students. Vaughan is of the idea that blended learning definition should not be narrowed but expanded to include the design of the course and pedagogical process of delivering the course with the blended approach. Also Oliver and Tingwell (2012), argued that blended learning will become redundant when it is seen as the practice of mixing traditional classroom approach with technology. Earlier on, Singh (2003) had opined that blended learning is based on the fact that learning is not a one-time act but a continuous process that incorporates various learning media. Blended learning refer to the planned implementation of a learning model that integrates student-centred, traditional in-class learning with other flexible learning methodologies using mobile and web-based online (especially collaborative) approaches in order to realise strategic advantages for the education system. This shows that the blending process has to be

properly planned and deliberately structured with the integration of appropriate technologies that will aid in realising the strategic goals set. Furthermore, Aretio (2018) defined blended learning as “an integration of means, resources, technologies, methodologies, activities, strategies and, both face-to-face and distance learning techniques to satisfy each specific learning need”. From the above definitions, one could say that blended learning is not mainly a combination of online and offline learning. It could be seen as a combination of various educational methods, approaches and techniques to achieve a particular learning goal. With the various definitions that several authors have given concerning blended learning and in view of the arguments, in this study blended learning is viewed as the deliberate combination of aspects of conventional face-to-face instruction with online learning approach, taking into consideration the design and pedagogy, to produce a blend that is more student-centered and encourages self-paced learning. Blended learning, if well planned, designed and implemented will provide learners with several opportunities such as improved learning and grades; ability to manage their time well; technology and communication skills that may help them academically and generally in life (Cleveland-Innes & Wilton, 2018). According to Lalima & angwal, (2017), many studies have shown that combining the traditional mode of instruction with online learning mediates the challenges of traditional learning and online learning since it enables learners to learn, get guidance and assist each other anytime and anywhere. Fakhir (2015) argues that adopting blended learning strategy should be considered quickly and effectively, since the traditional ways and styles of learning will not be enough for the coming era. Allen and Seaman (2006) posits that in the United States, blended learning is being used by 63% of school districts. However, in a majority of schools in most developing countries like Nigeria blended learning is still not yet used.

Types of Blended Learning Models

According to Horn and Staker (2014a), there are four major models of blended. They are:

- 1. Rotation Model:** The rotation model is a type of blended learning where students rotate through different learning modalities, at least one of which is online learning. Common rotation models include station rotation, lab rotation, and flipped classroom. In the station rotation model, students rotate through different stations, such as small-group instruction, independent online learning, and collaborative activities. The lab rotation model involves students rotating between a physical classroom and a computer lab or learning lab for online learning. The flipped classroom model has students engage with online content at home and then participate in active learning activities in the classroom.
- 2. Self-Blend:** In the self-blend model, students choose to take one or more courses entirely online to supplement their traditional, face-to-face course load. Students have the flexibility to customize their learning experiences by selecting online courses that align with their interests, needs, or schedules. This model allows students to take ownership of their learning and tailor their educational path. The self-blend model is often used in high schools and colleges, where students have more autonomy in their course selections.
- 3. Self-Directed Model:** The self-directed model, also known as the self-paced model, is a learning approach where students take full responsibility for their learning. Students work independently, set their own learning goals, determine the pace of their learning, and choose the resources and strategies they will use. This model relies heavily on the learner's ability to self-regulate, be motivated, and

manage their time effectively. The self-directed model is often used in online or distance learning environments, where students have more flexibility and control over their learning process.

4. Enriched Virtual Model: The enriched virtual model is a form of blended learning where students primarily engage in online learning, with occasional face-to-face interactions or sessions. In this model, students may attend a physical school campus for specific activities, such as labs, group projects, or face-to-face instruction, while the majority of their learning takes place online. The enriched virtual model aims to provide the benefits of online learning, such as flexibility and personalization, while also incorporating some face-to-face elements to support student engagement and social interactions. This model is often used in schools or districts that want to offer online learning options while still maintaining a physical school presence. These learning models offer different approaches to integrating technology, personalization, and flexibility into the educational process, catering to the diverse needs and preferences of students.

Benefits of Blended Learning Approach

In blended learning approach, the teacher attempts to synchronize face-to-face learning experience with online learning experiences to give the students a taste of the two approaches. Each approach complements the other. For instance, lecture materials can be provided online for students to study whenever and wherever they are able to connect to the internet, thereby freeing up class time which can be used for more practical examples and explanations (Kiviniemi, 2014). In the traditional face-to-face approach, the teacher pilots the helm of affairs and is the center of attraction, the originator and director of the learning process. However, in the blended learning approach, the learner takes the center stage and the interaction between teacher and learner becomes much more flexible (Anh, 2017). In the blended learning approach the teacher is only a facilitator of the process while the learners are engaged in active learning. Blended Learning Approach brings together the advantages of the traditional face-to-face learning and those of online learning (Kose, 2010; Benson, Anderson, & Ooms, 2011) and helps to reduce the disadvantages of the two approaches (Pima, Odetayo, Iqbal, & Sedoyeta, 2018). However, online learning provides time-flexibility, place-flexibility (Gecer, 2013) and takes into consideration individual learning style and speed, which are not catered for in the traditional face-to-face approach. Studies have shown that the blended learning approach can offer several benefits for students, including increased engagement, improved time management, and greater flexibility in learning (Means, Toyama, Murphy, Bakia, & Jones, (2009). Blended learning can also lead to higher levels of academic achievement by providing students with more personalized and interactive learning experiences (Boelens, De Wever, & Voet, 2017).

Concept of academic achievement

Achievement refers to the attainment level of a pre-set goal after a specific period of time. According to Afzal and Afzal (2015), achievement has to do with the completion of a task, an attainment and accomplishment after a specified period of training. Academic achievement refers to the attainment of outcomes that are tied to educational experiences (York, Gibson, & Rankin, 2015). Students are exposed to educational experiences within a given period and then assessed to see the outcomes of such exposure. The results of the assessments are computed and then used as the achievement of the students. Osokoya, as cited in Ogundokun and Adeyemo (2010), defined academic achievement as the product of the learning experience offered to students. It is the outcome of instruction and a measure of what the students have learned during the teaching-learning process. Several authors have tried to

differentiate between the terms, academic performance and academic achievement. On the contrary, Afzal and Afzal (2015) did not see any difference between the two terms. In this study, academic achievement referred to the students' scores in the achievement test administered to them. Iji pointed out that academic achievement is measured in terms of retention. Eze, Ezenwafor and Obidile defined retention to be "the ability to recall or remember what has been taught after a given time as a measure of students' progress. Students' retention level is vital to their learning and the teacher ought to know this. Hafeez and Aamir (2014) explained retention to mean the process of storing encoded information or events and recalling them in responses to external stimuli. Also, Parker (2009) defined retention as the ability to remember facts and other information. It is the ability to keep the possession of knowledge of lesson learnt and to recall or apply such knowledge when it is required (Safo, Ezenwa & Wushishi, 2013). For this study, retention is defined as the ability of students to recall what they have been taught.

Comparing Academic Achievement in Public and Private Schools Using Blended Learning and Face to Face Approach

Studies have shown that the implementation of blended learning in public secondary schools can have a positive impact on students' academic achievement in accounting subjects. A study by Owolabi and Aluko (2020) found that public secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria, who were taught using a blended learning approach demonstrated significantly higher academic performance compared to those taught using the traditional lecture-based method. Adewale and Ogunleye (2021) reported that the integration of technology-enhanced learning strategies, such as online simulations and interactive assessments, helped to improve the understanding and problem-solving skills of public school students. Akinola and Oluwatobi (2019) conducted a study in Lagos State and found that private school students who experienced a blended learning environment in their accounting classes outperformed their counterparts in the traditional classroom setting. Ogunkunle and Odekunle (2020) reported that private secondary school students exhibited higher levels of engagement, motivation, and academic achievement in accounting subjects when exposed to a well-designed blended learning curriculum. Adebayo and Balogun (2021) conducted a comparative analysis in Lagos State and found that both public and private school students showed significant improvements in their performance when taught using the blended learning approach, with private school students demonstrating slightly higher academic achievements.

The theoretical Framework is hinged on Connectivism Learning Theory by Siemens and Downes (2005). The theory describes how people in the digital age learn through transfer and sharing of information over the internet. The proponents of this theory are Siemens (2005) and Downes (2010) tried to explain how the internet and all its applications have facilitated the way people share information and learn in an age that is technologically advancing. The theory posits that learning starts when a learner connects to a learning community (online) and shares knowledge with members of the community (Kop & Hill, 2008). Learning community here, refers to a coming together of like-minds who have the same interests and they encourage dialogue, information sharing, interaction and discussions. Connectivism to Duke, Harper, and Johnston (2013:6) is "social learning that is facilitated by a network of people (called the learning group) who share knowledge across a network of connections, which means that learning involves having the ability to connect with other people. In connectivism, learning groups are seen as "nodes" which refer to the connection points that are found on a network. These connection points, which could be two or more on a network, enable the sharing

of information on the network. The strength of the node will depend on the level of information transferred between them (Downes cited by Kop & Hill, 2008). According to Siemens (2005), learning occurs within an unclear environment that is ever changing especially in a digital era. Siemens therefore gave the following principles of connectivism:

- a) Learning and knowledge rests in diversity of opinions.
- b) Learning is a process of connecting specialized nodes or information sources.
- c) Learning may reside in non-human appliances.
- d) Capacity to know more is more critical than what is currently known
- e) Nurturing and maintaining connections is needed to facilitate continual learning.
- f) Ability to see connections between fields, ideas, and concepts is a core skill.
- g) Currency (accurate, up-to-date knowledge) is the intent of all connectivism learning.
- h) Decision-making is a learning process. Choosing what to learn and the meaning of incoming information is seen through the lens of a shifting reality. While there is a right answer now, it may be wrong tomorrow due to alterations in the information climate affecting the decision.

The implication of the connectivism learning theory to blended learning is that the teacher should be able to create a learning environment in which students can connect with each other through discussion forum, chats, emails and peer review assignments.

Empirical review on academic achievement of male and female students in both private and public schools using blended learning approach

Okocha, Eyiolorunshe, and Oguntayo (2016) carried out a study on students' acceptance of blended learning in Nigeria to determine the level of acceptance that undergraduate students have towards blended learning. The results revealed that the students were more interested in the lecture materials and resources placed online in the Learning Management System than on the discussions and interactions that go on in the classroom. One major finding of the study was that gender did not significantly affect the user acceptance of blended learning. This result contradicted the views of Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, and Davis (2003), and Venkatesh and Morris (2000) who reported that gender had a great role to play in technology acceptance. Noni, Abdullah and Ismail (2017) conducted a study to determine the level of satisfaction that students had in blended learning approach and to determine the student's preferred blended learning construct. The results show that gender did not significantly influence the perception that students had on the level of satisfaction towards blended learning environment. A study by Vernadakis et al (2012) carried out at the Democritus University of Thrace in Greece, investigated the impact of traditional and blended instruction, on students' performance in Physical Education in an Early Childhood course. The results of the study showed that there were significant differences between students who attended the traditional course and those who attended the blended method instruction ($t(51) = 2.66, p > .05$), with students who attended the course with blended instruction showing higher performance. Thus it was concluded that blended learning improved student's performance in Physical Education Early Childhood better than traditional learning. Another study was done by Tseng, Kano, Hsu (2014) in Taiwan to determine the effect of integrating blended teaching into Mathematics learning for Junior High School students. The findings of the study showed that learning effectiveness of "blended teaching" was significantly better than that of "traditional instruction". Thus it was also concluded that integrating blended learning into the teaching of Mathematics improved the learning effectiveness.

Al-Madani (2015) in Saud Arabia investigated the effect of Blended Learning approach compared to the traditional learning approach on fifth grade student’s achievement in the development of their verbal creative thinking. The study concluded that using the blended approach was more effective than the traditional method in terms of achievement and the development of verbal creative thinking skills. Celyan and Kesici (2017) investigated the effects of blended learning on the middle school students’ academic achievement level and product evaluation scores. The findings showed that the learners who were taught using blended learning performed significantly better than those taught using traditional learning.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Lagos state comprises six educational districts. A school was selected from each district using multistage sampling technique and 5 students from each school using random sampling method. The study design used Quasi-experimental design, hence the students from intact classes from each selected schools were classified into experimental group and control group and were taught a new topic in commerce. The two intact classes were 30 commercial senior secondary III students randomly selected for the study (15 students from each group). Since there is a standard curriculum for all schools in Lagos state thus, the same topic was taught in all the schools. A pre-test was conducted by the researcher and the subject teachers of the selected schools and topics on both the control and experimental groups to measure their level of attainment in the topic. The principal instruments for the test was termed Commerce Achievement Test (CAT) which contains twenty-five (25) multiple choice objective questions. After the pre-test, the experimental group was taught using blended learning approach while the control group was taught still using the conventional learning approach. After the treatment lessons, post-test was administered on the two groups under thorough supervision after one week to test their level of achievement. The study design is illustrated below:

Presentation of Data

This presentation was done to answer the research questions raised.

Table 1: Comparing impact of blended learning approach with conventional classroom approach on students’ academic achievement

Approach	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference	Remark
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Blended Learning Approach	15	33.24	12.17	63.06	10.96	29.82	BLA has more effect than CCA
Conventional Approach	15	24.63	9.35	33.23	13.33	8.60	

Data in Table 1 show that the mean score of the pre-test for experimental group (BLA) was 33.24 while the post-test mean score is 63.06. This signifies a mean difference of 29.82. On the other hand, the mean score of the pre-test for the control group (CCA) is 24.63 while the post-test mean score is 33.23. The control group also has a mean difference of 8.60. The results therefore indicate that blended learning approach has a higher effect on students' academic achievement scores when compared with conventional classroom approach. The result shows that students in the treatment group taught using the blended learning approach obtained a higher mean achievement score than those in the control group who were taught using the traditional learning approach. This finding agrees with the finding of Thompson, (2011) who indicates that, using a blended classroom led to remarkable academic performance and positive attitude that could increase interaction between teachers and learners. Although the two approaches had positive effects, the blended learning approach had a higher positive effect on the students' achievement scores than the conventional approach. The results of this study is also in line with those of Lopez-Perez, Perez-Lopez, and Rodriguez-Ariza (2013) who found out that blended learning approach had a positive effect on undergraduate students' performance in four different business programmes. It was noted also that the application of blended learning could increase students' engagement and improve their performance which is in agreement with this study. The results are in line with those of Marchalot, Dureuil, Veber, Fellahi, Hanouz, Dupont, & Compere (2017) and Gogo (2018), who discovered a significant difference in the performance of students taught with blended learning models from those taught with face-to face approaches. In the contrary, Jones and Chen (2008) did not discover a significant difference in students' outcomes in the two approaches. They found out that blended learning approach fell short in areas like students engagement and teacher preparedness. Keller, John, Sally, and James (2009) also pointed out that there was no difference between blended learning and traditional learning approaches. This may be based on the pattern of employment of blended learning. Moreso, Berge & Yi-ping, (2004) opines that blended learning approach may increase students' participation level, there is the possibility of high-drop out and distractions from technology usage in blended learning approach which may not be present in conventional face-to-face approach.

Table 2: Results showing the effect of blended learning approach on achievement scores of male and female students.

Approach	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference	Remark
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Male Students	15	36.47	13.69	66.06	9.72	29.59	BLA had more effect on female students' achievement
Female Students	15	30.00	10.22	60.06	11.39	30.06	

Table 2 indicates that male students taught with blended learning approach have mean achievement scores of 36.47 and 66.06 for the pre-test and post-test respectively. This results in a mean difference of 29.59. On the other hand, the female students taught with blended learning approach have mean achievement scores of 30.00 and 60.06 for the pre-test and post-test respectively. Also, the female

students have a mean difference of 30.06. The results show that the female students taught with blended learning approach have a higher mean difference than their male counterparts. It therefore means that blended learning approach have more effect on female students' achievement scores than on that of the male students. It therefore means that blended learning approach had more effect on female students' achievement scores than on that of the male students. It also reveals that there is slight difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught using blended learning approach. This finding agrees with the findings of Beard and Burrell (2010). However, the result of this finding disagrees with the findings of Torty (2010), that gender has no significant influence on students' achievement. The finding is contrary to the findings of Du (2011) and Gogo (2018) who discovered that male students performed better than the female students on an e-learning course taught with a blended learning approach.

Table 3: Results showing mean achievement of male and female students taught using blended learning approach in public and private schools.

Approach	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference	Remark
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Public School Students	15	35.53	5.72	61.45	6.1	25.92	BLA had more effect on Private School Students' achievement
Private School Students	15	36.33	5.8	72.00	5.26	35.67	

Results in table 3 above shows that public school students had a pretest mean of 35.53 with a standard deviation of 5.72 and a posttest mean of 61.45 with a standard deviation of 61.0. The difference between the pretest and posttest mean for public school students was 25.92. The private school students had a pretest mean of 36.33 with a standard deviation of 5.8 and a posttest mean of 72.00 with a standard deviation of 5.26. The difference between the pretest and posttest mean for the private school students was 35.67. However, for each of the groups, the posttest means were greater than the pretest means with the private school students having higher mean gain. This is an indication that blended learning approach has significant effect on both private school students and public school students. The standard deviation of the private school students is higher than those of the public school students which means that the scores of the private school students have more variability from the mean than those of the public school students. The results show that the private school students taught with blended learning approach had a higher mean difference than their public school counterparts. It therefore means that blended learning approach had more effect on private school students' achievement scores than on that of the public school students.

Conclusion and recommendation

From the findings of the study, it is concluded that blended learning approach has a higher effect on students' achievement than the conventional classroom approach. This is because blended learning approach encourages self-paced learning, increased students' participation and is more student-friendly than the conventional classroom approach. Although, blended learning modalities may require

more effort from the teacher (especially at the initial stages), students are more engaged in the learning process thereby increasing their interaction with the learning materials. It was also concluded that students' gender did not significantly affect their academic achievement whether they were taught with either blended learning approach or face-to-face approach. By addressing the identified implications and pursuing further research, educators and policymakers can better harness the benefits of blended learning to support student success. Consequently, accounting teachers and accounting educators have a great responsibility to attempt integrating blending learning models into their instructional strategy. Learning content have to be reorganized in such a way as to enable students have the opportunity to learn at their own speed and time. Educators will need to be trained on how to use learning management systems, like Moodle, Blackboard, and Edmodo and so on, to facilitate learning especially at the tertiary levels. It was therefore recommended that blended learning approach be adopted in the teaching and learning of in senior secondary schools in Nigeria and that Educators should adopt the flipped classroom model of blended learning approach in the teaching of their subjects as it has a higher effect on students' academic achievement and retention. Government and other stakeholders in education should see to the problem of inadequacy of facilities and the necessary technological infrastructures that have made the full integration of online learning difficult. Electric power, internet connectivity, training and professional development of teachers should be considered and fast tracked to ensure the successful implementation of blended learning and foster equitable access to quality education.

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